

Photochemical Reactions in Circularly Polarised, Plane Polarised and Ordinary Light.

The Velocity of Reactions between Bromine and
(1) Cinnamic Acid, (2) Stilbene.

BY

JNANENDRA CHANDRA GHOSH

AND

RUKMINI MOHAN PURKAYESTHA.

The reaction between bromine and cinnamic acid has been investigated by Herz and Mylius (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3816), and that between bromine and stilbene by Bauer and Moser (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 918). The dibromo derivatives are stable in both cases, and the reactions proceed to completion. The velocity of these reactions in darkness is negligibly small when carbon tetrachloride is used as solvent.

Byk (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 1904, 49, 641) suggested that synthesis of a compound containing asymmetric carbon atom by circularly polarised light might lead to the formation of one of the optical isomers in a preponderating ratio; but the recent work of Bredig (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1923, 62, 456) has not confirmed this hypothesis. From the present investigation it appears very probable to us that the velocity of the above reactions does not only depend on the intensity of light but also on the quality of light.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Point-o-lite 100 c.p. lamp *P* (Fig. 1) was run at 110 volts from a battery of accumulators; *L* was a convex lens

for obtaining a parallel beam of light. T and T' are rectangular glass vessels with plane parallel sides filled with $N/50$ copper sulphate solution (4 cm. thick) and with normal potassium nitrite solution (1 cm. thick) respectively. The first filter cuts off heat rays completely and part of the red light and the second, ultraviolet radiations beyond $390 \mu\mu$ (*vide* Ghosh and Biswas, *Z. Elektro-chem.*, 1924, 30, 97). The polariser P' consisted of a large nicol, 4.5 cm. aperture, which gave a horizontal beam of polarised light. It was so arranged that the plane of polarisation of the emergent beam was inclined at an angle of 45° to the horizontal plane. The Fresnel Rhomb F was set up with its faces vertical, and the emergent circularly polarised light passed through the aperture ($2.5 \text{ cm.} \times 2.5 \text{ cm.}$) of a screen S , into the reaction vessel R ($2.5 \times 2.5 \times 2 \text{ cm.}$). This vessel was enclosed in a double jacketed copper box with plane parallel glass windows through which water was continuously circulated from a thermostat by means of a pump. The temperature was kept constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$. The intensity of light was measured by means of a radio-micrometer placed behind the copper box and was varied by using lenses of different focal lengths, the point arc of the lamp being always at the focal distance of the lens. When ordinary parallel light was used for experiment, a canada balsam film between two plane glass plates was interposed between the screen S and the filters, so that light, in all the experiments recorded here, passed through a film of canada balsam. It is well known that the absorption and reflection co-efficient of colourless optical glass is independent of wave-lengths between $760 \mu\mu$ and $390 \mu\mu$ and therefore the distribution of intensities of light over the various wave-lengths remained identical in experiments with ordinary, plane polarised and circularly polarised light. As a matter of fact the

transmission co-efficient of plane parallel glass plates used in these investigations was about 98% .

The concentration of bromine in the reaction chamber was measured by means of König Martens Spectrophotometer, *SP*. Table I gives the concentration of bromine corresponding to $\log \frac{\tan \alpha}{\tan \alpha_0}$ for the green light ($546\mu\mu$) used in these measurements. The exact proportionality between the concentration and $\log \frac{\tan \alpha}{\tan \alpha_0}$ is evident and hence concentration of bromine can be easily calculated by interpolation from this table.

TABLE I

Concentration of bromine	$\log \frac{\tan \alpha}{\tan \alpha_0}$
·01742	·6925
·01635	·6464
·01348	·5833
·01214	·4718
·01012	·3933
·00867	·3418
·00639	·2578
·00485	·1948
·00323	·1275

Bromine, stilbene, cinnamic acid and carbon tetrachloride (used as solvent) were all obtained from Kahlbaum and were further purified in the laboratory.

The molecular extinction co-efficient of bromine for light transmitted through the filters used in this investigation as measured by the radio-micrometer is given in Table II.

TABLE II

Light through cell	Deflection of radiomicro- meter	Molecular extinction co-efficient of bromine for light transmitted through filters
(1) Filled with CCl_4 ...	261	...
(2) Filled with .01823 Mol. Br solution.	223	1.68
(3) Filled with .00811 Mol. Br solution.	239	1.88

TABLE III

Cinnamic acid0425 M
Bromine01825 M
Temp.	26°C

Intensity of light = 228 mm. deflection of radiomicrometer.

Time in minutes	Conc. of Br	$k \times 10^4$
0	.01825	...
35	.01357	823
65.5	.01057	833
97	.00817	826
130	.00653	820
167	.00465	817

In Table III the velocity co-efficients are calculated on the basis of a unimolecular equation and it is evident that the values are identical within the limits of experimental error.

From Table IV it will be further noticed that the velocity constant is not exactly proportional to the intensity of incident light. The reason for this anomaly is not clear.

TABLE IV(a)

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Conc. of cinnamic acid	Intensity with aqueous filter only	$k \times 10^4$
26°	·0182 M	·0429 M	160	423
26°	·0182 M	·0429 M	360	817

TABLE IV(b)

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Conc. of stilbene	Intensity with aqueous filter only	$k \times 10^4$
26°	·0182 M	·022 M	160	283
26°	·0182 M	·022 M	360	570

Table V makes it quite clear that the velocity co-efficient is quite independent of the initial concentration of bromine but increases as the initial concentration of stilbene increases. The intensity of light was throughout the same in all these experiments.

TABLE V

Temperature—6°C.

Conc. of Br	Conc. of stilbene	$k \times 10^4$
·0182 M	·022 M	476
·0091 M	·022 M	483
·0118 M	·022 M	478
·0118 M	·011 M	446

Exactly similar results have been found in the bromination of cinnamic acid. According to present theories of photochemical reactions the photo-active molecules get excited by the absorption of radiant energy, and the

end products are the results of dark reaction which might be the spontaneous decomposition of these excited molecules. If this view were correct then in the reaction between bromine and stilbene or cinnamic acid, the latter must be considered as the acceptor molecules, while bromine should be regarded as the photo-active molecule which gets excited by the absorption of radiant energy. The rate of production of excited bromine molecules per unit volume of solution is proportional to the amount of radiation absorbed at any instant and is given by

$$\frac{d[\text{Br excited}]}{dt} = KI_0 \left[1 - e^{-\epsilon(a-x)} \right]$$

where $(a-x)$ is the concentration of bromine at any instant and I_0 is the intensity of incident light and ϵ , the molecular extinction co-efficient.

Now we have already seen that the value of ϵ is small (*vide* Table II) and therefore

$$\left[1 - e^{-\epsilon(a-x)} \right]$$

may be taken to be equal to $\epsilon(a-x)$.

The rate of production of excited bromine molecules is thus proportional to the concentration of bromine molecules at any instant for the same intensity of incident radiation and is given by $KI_0 \epsilon(a-x)$. Now if τ be the life period of excited molecules and T be the interval between two successive collisions between an excited bromine molecule and an acceptor stilbene molecule then the rate of production of stilbene dibromide is given by

$$KI_0 \epsilon(a-x) \frac{\tau}{T+\tau} \text{ (Turner, } \textit{Phys. Rev.}, \textit{1924}, \textit{23}, \textit{464)}$$

The rate of production of stilbene dibromide is the same as the rate of disappearance of bromine and therefore

we obtain

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = KI_0 \epsilon^{(a-x)} \times \frac{\tau}{T+\tau}$$

which is the equation for a monomolecular reaction provided T remains constant during the progress of the reaction. The constant k , for monomolecular reaction is therefore equal to

$$KI_0 \epsilon \frac{\tau}{T+\tau} \quad \text{or} \quad C \frac{\tau}{T+\tau} \quad \text{where } C=KI_0 \epsilon.$$

Now assuming that the kinetic theory can be extended to dilute solutions,

$$T = \frac{1}{Aa^2p}$$

where

$$A = 2666 \cdot 6 \sqrt{\frac{2\sqrt{2}N}{K} \cdot \frac{m_1+m_2}{m_1 m_2}}$$

(m_1 and m_2 are the molecular weights of bromine and stilbene respectively; N , Avogadro number, and $K=1 \cdot 37 \times 10^{-16}$; a , the distance between the centres of two reacting molecules and p the osmotic pressure of the acceptor molecules in millimeters of mercury. It is clear that T remains constant during the progress of a reaction if p remains constant, *i.e.*, if the concentration of the acceptor molecules is in excess. This has been always the case in our experiments.

It will be noticed that the value of K_1 should be independent of the concentration of bromine which has been actually found to be the case. The value of K_1 should, however, depend on the value of T , *i.e.*, on p , the osmotic pressure of acceptor molecules.

$$K_1 = C \frac{\tau}{T+\tau} = C \frac{1}{1+\frac{T}{\tau}} = C \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{Aa^2pr}}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{1}{K_1} = \frac{1}{C} \left[1 + \frac{1}{Aa^2pr} \right] = \frac{1}{C} + \frac{1}{CAa^2pr}$$

that is, the inverse of the velocity constant should be a linear function of the inverse of the osmotic pressure of acceptor molecules and hence of the concentration.

The values of the velocity constants for varying initial concentration of cinnamic acid and the same initial concentration of bromine, the intensity of radiation remaining same in all the experiments, are given in Table VI. It will be seen that as the initial concentration of cinnamic acid increases the velocity co-efficient also increases and in Fig. II, graph I is plotted by taking $1/k_1$ as abscissa and $1/p$ as ordinate. It will be evident that as required by theory, the graph obtained is a straight line. From the slope of the curve and the value of the intercept on the abscissa, we can, following Turner, calculate the life period of excited bromine molecules.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{1}{CA\alpha^2\tau} \text{ and Intercept} = \frac{1}{C}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \frac{\text{slope}}{\text{intercept}} = \frac{1}{A\alpha^2\tau}$$

TABLE VI

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Osmotic pressure of cinnamic acid in mm. calculated from concentration	K, (velocity co-efficient)
24.5°	.005485 M	180.8	.03015
		120.6	.02668
		80.4	.02406
		60.3	.02077
		40.2	.01674
		30.15	.01440
		20.1	.01122

In this case the value of A is 27.29×10^{20} and from the curve the value of $A\alpha^2\tau$ is found to be 21.5×10^{-8} assuming $\alpha = 10^{-7}$ cm. the value of τ comes out to be 0.8×10^{-9} sec.

FIG. II.

Each side = 12 units

TABLE VII

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Osmotic pressure of stilbene in mm. calculated from concentration	K, (velocity co-efficient)
24°	.005485 M	249.7	.012
		62.43	.01035
		41.62	.00943
		20.81	.00722
		13.87	.00596

Table VII gives the values of velocity co efficient for varying initial concentration of stilbene, and in Fig. II, graph II is plotted by taking $1/k$ as abscissa and $1/p$ as ordinate. Here too the requirements of theory are fulfilled for the graph is a straight line.

From the curve, $Aa^2\tau = 60.5 \times 10^{-3}$ and in this case A is 26.01×10^{20} . This gives $\tau = 2.33 \times 10^{-9}$ sec.

Velocities of Photo-bromination for the same Intensities of Ordinary, Plane Polarised and Circularly Polarised Light.

The intensities of plane polarised, circularly polarised and ordinary light were made as far as possible the same by suitable selection of lenses and placing the point arc at the focal distances of the lenses. The current and the voltage used for the lamp were never varied. Hence the distribution of intensities over the various frequencies in the beam of white light remained the same in all experiments. As has been already mentioned before, the absorption and reflection co-efficients of the glasses are the same for all wave-lengths between 760 and 400 $\mu\mu$ and therefore the quality of light in these experiments is identical excepting for the state of polarisation.

Tables VIII—XIII give the velocity co-efficients for photo-bromination of cinnamic acid and of stilbene in ordinary plane polarised and circularly polarised light. The experimental data for each experiment are reproduced in detail so as to indicate the relative variation in the values of the velocity co-efficients. Again each experiment was repeated several times and the reproductibility of the velocity co-efficients is shown by recording the data obtained in a duplicate experiment. In Tables XIV and XV is given a summary of the results. It will be noticed that for the same intensity, ordinary light and plane polarised light are equally effective, while circularly polarised light appears to be less effective. We do not intend at present to lay great stress on this observation, but unless there has been a systematic error in our observations or in our experimental arrangement, which we have not been able to detect, the data recorded here appear convincing.

TABLE VIII

Concentration of cinnamic acid—0.425 M
 Concentration of bromine —0.1825 M
 Temperature —26°C

Ordinary Light.

Intensity of radiation = 229 mm. of radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$	Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$
0	·01825	—	0	·01825	—
40	·0132	810	30	·0143	812
80	·0098	832	65	·01053	843
130	·0064	805	94	·00821	814
185	·00401	826	145	·0067	808
240	·0038	(738)			
		Mean 818			Mean 818

$$K_1 = 818 \times 10^{-5}$$

TABLE IX

Plane polarised Light.

Intensity of radiation = 228 mm. of radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$	Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$
0	·01825	—	0	·01825	—
35·5	·01857	835	36	·0135	835
65·5	·01057	832	76·5	·009525	839
97	·00817	828	108	·007425	830
127	·0·658	807	142	·0057	816
167	·00465	816	188	·00401	805
		Mean 824			Mean 825

Hence $K_p = 825 \times 10^{-5}$

TABLE X

Circularly polarised Light.

Intensity of radiation = 218 mm. of radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$	Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^5$
0	·01825	—	0	·01825	—
35	·01396	766	38	·01365	741
69	·01068	775	72	·01057	757
100	·00843	770	117	·00761	748
150	·006	741	154	·00577	745
209	·0041	(713)			
		Mean 764			Mean 748

Hence $K_s = 756 \times 10^{-5}$

Concentration of stilbene—·022 M

Concentration of bromine—·01825 M

Temperature —26°C.

TABLE XI

Ordinary Light.

Intensity of radiation = 229 mm. radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^4$
0	·01825	—
40	·0147	540
75	·01241	513
120	·0099	508
160	·0084	(483)
		Mean 520

Hence $K_p = 520 \times 10^{-5}$

TABLE XII

Plane polarised Light

Intensity of radiation = 228 mm. radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^4$	Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^4$
0	·01825	—	0	·01825	—
49	·01395	547	70	·01252	538
99	·0108	529	109	·01088	526
160	·0087	497	155	·00847	495
		Mean 524			Mean 519

 $K_p = 522 \times 10^{-5}$

TABLE XIII

Circularly polarised Light.

Intensity of radiation = 218 mm. radio-micrometer deflection.

Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^4$	Time	Conc. of Br	$K_1 \times 10^4$
0	·01825	—	0	·01825	—
59	·01872	485	53	·01402	496
101	·01132	472	100	·011325	476
162	·009	437	160	·008942	446
230	·00705	493	204	·00772	433
		Mean 457			Mean 463

$$K_c = 460 \times 10^{-5}$$

TABLE XIV

Temp.	Conc. of Bromine	Conc. of Cinnamic acid.	I,	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$	I,	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$	Ic	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$
26°C	·01825M	·0425M	229	818	228	825	218	756

TABLE XV

Temp	Conc. of Bromine	Conc. of Stilbene	I,	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$	I,	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$	I,	$K_c \times 10^{-5}$
26°C	·01825	·022M	229	520	228	522	218	480

Temperature Co-efficient of K.

The majority of photochemical reactions have very small temperature co-efficients; for a large number of reactions the value is unity (Plotnikow, *Lehrbuch der Photochemie*, p. 63). Dhar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1857) gives for the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine, sodium formate and mercuric chloride, the high

values 2.68 and 2.94 respectively. As Tables XVI and XVII will show the temperature co-efficient of these reactions is 2.6—2.8.

TABLE XVI

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Conc. of Stilbene	$k_1 \times 10^4$
23°	.01176	.022	214
33°	"	"	561
43°	"	"	1424

TABLE XVII

Temp.	Conc. of Br	Conc. of cinnamic acid	$k_1 \times 10^4$
32.5°	.01618	.0429	807
42.5°	.01618	"	2272

Tolman (*J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 2285) considers that molecules in the lower quantum states may not be in a condition to absorb radiant energy of the frequency used or the energy level, which they attain after the absorption, may not be high enough to lead to chemical reaction and obtains the relation,

$$\frac{d \log K_v}{dT} = \frac{\bar{E} - \bar{E}}{KT^2}$$

where \bar{E} is the average energy before activation of those molecules only which pick up radiant energy and react and \bar{E} the average energy of all the molecules. In a large number of cases $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ is zero and the temperature co-efficient is unity. In these reactions obviously $\bar{E} - \bar{E}$ has a large positive value, thus accounting for a large temperature co-efficients observed.

*Application of Einstein's Law of Photochemical
Equivalence.*

Noddak (*Z. Electro-chem.*, 1921, 27, 360) finds that in reaction between bromine vapour and cyclohexane Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence holds good. The large temperature co-efficient observed rules out that possibility in the present case. With the aid of the available data it is possible to calculate roughly the ratio of the number of molecules that enter into photochemical reaction and the number of quanta of radiant energy absorbed. The radio-micrometer was calibrated by means of a Hefner lamp which according to Gerlach (*Physik. Zeit.*, 1913, 14, 577) radiates 900 ergs per sec. on a surface of one sq. cm. at a distance of one metre. It was found that one erg per one sq. cm. produces a deflection of 1.22 mm. in the radio-micrometer. Noddak takes $470\mu\mu$ as the mean wavelength of light absorbed by bromine.

From Table II it is evident that the number of gm. mols. of bromine transformed is .00468 in 35 minutes. So the amount transformed per sec. per sq. cm. \times depth of reaction vessel (2.5 cm.) is

$$\frac{.00468 \times 2.5}{35 \times 60 \times 1000} \text{ or } 5.56 \times 10^{-9} \text{ mols.}$$

$$\text{or } 55.6 \times 10^{-10} \text{ mols.}$$

No. of quanta absorbed

$$\frac{230 \times \frac{1}{1.22} \left(1 - 10^{-1.78 \times 2.5^2 \times .01823} \right) \times 470 \times 10^{-7}}{6.07 \times 10^{22} \times 6.5 \times 10^{-27} \times 3 \times 10^{10}} = .128 \times 10^{-10}$$

* 2.5 cm. is the depth of the reaction vessel.

It thus appears that one quantum of energy at 26° leads to the formation of 436 molecules of dibromocinnamic acid. In the case of stilbene the number of molecules of the dibromo derivative formed per quantum of energy at 26° comes out to be 305. Eggert (*Physik. Zeit.*, 1924, 25, 19) finds that in the transformation of maleic ester to fumaric ester by bromine under the influence of light, the number of molecules transformed per quantum absorbed is 565. Nernst (*Z. Electro-chem.*, 1918, 24, 335) considers that similar high values by Bodenstein and Dux (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1923, 85, 297) in the combination of hydrogen and chlorine are due to a primary photochemical reaction being followed by secondary ones. There are no facts available which would justify the assumption that the above explanation of Nernst holds good in the reactions stated here.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
DACCA UNIVERSITY.

Received, September 5, 1925.
